

Machine Learning Based Mobile Forensics

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Abstract—Many portable electronic devices today, thanks to the development of smart mobile devices, can not only keep us connected but also act as a workspace and a source of entertainment. An individual may manage their job in a convenient way with the help of mobile devices and processor technology, and the equipment also has a variety of apps installed for various purposes. Criminal offences are hard to track down in the interim, and mobile services might be used by criminals to engage in destructive conduct. This research develops a machine learning-based framework to aid with the investigation

Keywords- Mobile forensics, linear svc, nntp

I. INTRODUCTION

The twenty-first century has seen an increase in cybercrime due to the rapid proliferation of the use of digital platforms in daily life. We use smart devices such as smartphone, tabs, lap tops etc. for various purposes in our life. This devices are the huge resources of information about an individual. Smart electronic equipment, such as computers and smartphones, used in criminal matters. Information from these devices can be used in different cases of investigation. We can use information obtained from a person's smart devices, for collecting call logs, email chats, photos and audios to figure out why they committed suicide. Mobile Forensics is the sub field of digital forensics that deals with crimes that have committed primarily via the use of smart electronics. The evidence from the smart devices are the valid sources in front of judiciary .But this process must be done by authorized authorities otherwise it will lead to a privacy breach, because the smart devices are very private area of a person. Machine learning holds the potential to support the mobile forensics investigation process .Machine learning models can detect abnormal behavior patterns and perform predictions. This study employs various machine learning models to make predictions by using Enron dataset. To use different machine learning and natural language processing techniques.

The method for detecting evidences from smart devices:

- Digital evidences can be gathered through a variety of sources. Obvious sources include computers, smart mobile phones, digital cameras, and so on. On-obvious sources include webpages that need to be maintained because they are subject to change.
- Seizure: The purpose of the seizure is to preserve evidence, the evidence will often be carried in the same condition to prevent a stop, which would change the files.

- Acquisition: This is the second phase in the mobile forensic process , in this case usually referring to the material recovery of material from a gadget

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

S. Somayeh, A. Seyed and S. Hosseini, [1] An important goal of digital forensics is to prepare reports accepted by the courts. Three important components of digital forensics are hard drive, 0memory, and network forensics which record and analyze certain trace of cybercriminal's behaviors

M. Reith, C. Carr and G. Gunsch, [2] The procedures and methods used in different locations to gather information and conduct investigations into these patterns are different.

Hadeer Ahmed, Issa Traore, and Sherif Saad [3],Method for both unsupervised partitioning of a sample of data and estimation of the possible number of inherent clusters that generate the data

L. Daniel, R. Maxwell and S. Spielman [4] created a new public dataset containing news article data. For automatic detection of fake news, they planned a machine learning strategy based on text processing. This has 87 accuracy percentage for associates in nursing. It has been discovered that this model excels at conveying the emotions of the text

K. J. Anil, C. Richard and Dubes [5]. This corpus can also be used for political human language technology analysis, rumour identification, subject modelling, argument mining, viewpoint classification, and topic modelling. The works in this area have made use of this standard. It's commendable that this is frequently limited to political information while others have included data from a variety of disciplines.

III. MOTIVATION

We live in a world that connects, socializes and interacts Via internet according to forbes2.5 quintillion bytes of data is created every day in 2018.Heavy use of social media fuels data creation that is generated from mobile phones. This facilities are widely used in crimes if we can collect, process, and analyses those information which can be used for several investigation purposes.

VI. METHODOLOGY

Finding a machine learning model that can spot data collecting fraud is the aim of this work. The Training and testing data sets are separated into two parts of the dataset. For the model to learn accurately, more data should be used during training.

Figure 1: Fraud Detection Methodology

The actions that must be taken are:

1. Data Collection
2. Data Pre-processing
3. Model Building
4. Analyzing
5. Result

A. Data Collection: Users have a dataset for detecting fraud, and the model is trained using the attributes of this dataset. The dataset represents a portion of the enormous Enron dataset. The titles and labels are in the columns. Emails from Enron Cooperation personnel are included in the data set. We are forecasting the fraud using this set of data.

B. Data Pre-processing: The first step in every machine learning technique is this one. This procedure makes use of data.

Cleaning, data reduction, data transformation, and cleaning. The dataset can also be cleared of the noisy data. To improve the accuracy of our model, the data can be processed. in order for the categorisation to be accurate.

C. Cleaning Data – First, the data is cleansed. In order to anticipate the fraud in the email data set using various models, users are deleting the undesirable noisy data in this area. unwelcome entrances. The dataset can also be cleared of the noisy data.

1. **Removing Stop words** – The datasets have stop words removed. These are the ones that pop up the most frequently yet aren't particularly significant in the text. This can be done in order to increase model accuracy.
2. **Splitting of Data** – From the datasets, the stop words are eliminated. These are the least significant ones in the text that appear the most frequently. This is something that can be done to improve the model's accuracy.

D. Machine Learning: Machine Learning has the potential to transform how forensic scientist's asses model evidence. Using several models,. is used to predict fraud in the email data set The different models are:

1. **Naïve Bayes-** One of the best classification techniques for creating short machine learning models that can make quick predictions is the naive Bayes classifier[6]. Naive Bayes classifiers in statistics are a family of straightforward probabilistic classifiers built on the Bayes theorem.

$$P(A/B)=P(B/A)P(A)/P(B)$$

2. **Linear svc** – In order to do classification and perform well with a high number of samples, the linear support vector classifier method [7] utilises a linear kernel function. Additional parameters for linear svc include loss function and penalty normalisation, which applies to "L1" or "L2." Since linear svc is dependent on the kernel linear method, the kernel method cannot be modified.
3. **Logistic regression**– This type os statistical model also called logit [8] model is often used for classification and predictive analysis. Logistic regression estimates the probability of an event occurring
4. **nltk library**– Using the nltk library simplifies the process of cleaning text, as it cleans emails sent to it by default(removes bad patterns ,stopwords,etc)
5. **Confusion matrix**– The performance of a classification mode on a set of test data for which the true values are known is sometimes described by a confusion matrix, which is a chart.

- 6. Recall**– The percentage of positive samples that were correctly identified as positive to all positive samples is used to calculate recall. Recall gauges how well a model can identify positive samples. More positive samples are found the higher the recall
- 7. Precision**– Precision measures a machine learning model's performance and the accuracy of a successful prediction it makes. Precision is calculated by dividing the total number of correct positive predictions by the number of genuine positives.

V. BUILD MODEL

The primary stage in detecting fraud is model creation. The algorithms are used by the user when developing the model. The involved actions are:

1. Import the packages that are necessary.

```
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import seaborn as sns
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from wordcloud import WordCloud
from nltk import Preprocessor
```

2. Load data set.

```
df = pd.read_csv('fraud_email_.csv')
df.head()
```

3. Visualization of target variables

4. Using nltk library text cleaning process

```
pre = Preprocessor(df['Emails']).text_cleaner()
```

5. Splitting the data set

```
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2, shuffle=True, random_state=42)
print(f'Splitting completed')
print(f'X Train: {len(X_train)} X Test: {len(X_test)} y Train: {len(y_train)} y Test: {len(y_test)}')
```

6. Fitting models

```
SVC_model = fit_predict(LinearSVC())

SVC_pred = SVC_model.predict(X_test)
LR_model = fit_predict(LogisticRegression())

LR_pred = LR_model.predict(X_test)
```

Fitting Model Completed.

Accuracy: 92.20452640402347

The accuracy is 98.4%.

7. Print the confusion matrix.

VII .RESULT

Digital forensics includes mobile forensics as a subset. The goal of mobile forensics is to recover pertinent data or digital evidence from a mobile device while maintaining the evidence's forensic status. The use of machine learning techniques is significant in this context. The linear model makes accurate and reliable predictions.

VII CONCLUSION

The goal of this research is to illustrate the mobile forensics procedure and how machine learning techniques aid in the prediction of evidence gathered from smart devices. Here, we'll use a subset of the enormous Enron email data set made up of fraud emails. We made predictions regarding the scam using a number of machine learning models. Using various machine learning techniques, we produce predictions on the scam. Which demonstrates that more essay can be written using machine learning to analyse the evidence. Due to the growing growth of cybercrime, this is crucial.

The Future application of the work has a lot of promise. We can use any data set with machine learning to boost the research by combining extra technologies like artificial intelligence and deep learning.

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